

Wf4Ever: Advanced Workflow Preservation Technologies for Enhanced Science

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D6.1 Addendum: Biological User Requirements

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This addendum provides a detailed list of Research Object user requirements for biology

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Change Log

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0.2	23-11-2011	Kristina Hettne	Revised document according to comments by Jose Manuel Gomez Perez
0.3	28-11-2011	Kristina Hettne, Aleix Garrido, Esteban Garcia Cuesta	Added text about how requirements relate to WP4.
0.4	1-12-2011	Kristina Hettne, Khalid Belhajjame, Graham Klyne	Added text about how requirements relate to WP2. Added picture illustrating the user scenario. Minor corrections in the text.
1.0	2-12-2011	Kristina Hettne, Rafael González Cabero, Marco Roos, Jose Enrique Ruiz	Added text about how requirements relate to WP3. Added picture illustrating the user scenario. Added conclusions.
1.1	2-12-2011	Marco Roos	Reorganised introduction and conclusion. Minor changes elsewhere.

Executive Summary

This document provides additional material for Deliverable D6.1 via a user scenario and newly extracted requirements relevant to the Genome Wide Association (GWA) case study performed at the Human Genetics Department of the Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC) to aid the development of Wf4Ever technology. The main goal is to provide a deeper insight on the GWA domain from the Wf4Ever perspective.

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1. Introduction

Deliverable D6.1 provides a general treatise of the genomics case studies and the requirements that we obtained from them (see Table 2 in D6.2 [1], section 7 in D2.1 [2], Tables 3-10 in D3.1 [3], and section 5.1.1 in D4.1 [5]). In this addendum we complement the requirement analysis with new data from the Metabolic Syndrome case in relation to newly compiled technical requirements, in particular we add

- ✦ More detail on a specific scenario for the Metabolic Syndrome case (the main case study)
- ✦ Newly collected or confirmed requirements from continued analysis after D6.1
- ✦ A reflection on technical requirements for each technical work package.

After submission of D6.1 we analysed specifically requirements for Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS). GWAS is an important advancement in Genomics that allows the study of genetic variations across all genes in large populations. This will be instrumental for our main case study: Metabolic Syndrome (MetS). At the Human Genetics department at the LUMC, metabolites have been associated with Metabolic Syndrome (MetS) traits and linked to Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) through GWAS. Here, we focus on user requirements for Wf4Ever related to the analysis of such metabolite-SNP associations. This analysis was inspired by newly compiled technical requirements, which we have related to the GWAS requirements in this addendum.

The addendum is organised as follows. In chapter 2 of this document we briefly introduce the requirement analysis methodology (section 2.1), present a GWAS scenario (section 2.2), and the requirements that we obtained from them including an estimate of personal benefit and impact in the community (section 2.3). In chapter 3 we reflect on the technical requirements for each technical work package, and conclude in chapter 4.

2. Methodology

2.1 Extracting user requirements

The method for extracting the user requirements have been described in Wf4Ever delivered technical reports [2-5], but for clarity we briefly summarise the procedure here. The starting point is a prose description of one or more user scenarios provided by the project's GWA user representative. From these, we extract a list of requirements following the popular agile development template "**As a** (*user/stakeholder type*) **I want** (*some capability*) **so that** (*some benefits that can be realized using that capability*)". This approach is intended to focus on extracting user requirements without regard to the technical mechanisms that might be employed to satisfy them; isolation of technical requirements is a separate process.

The method followed to produce the user requirements is:

1. **Isolate requirements:** read through a user-supplied scenario description and highlight any phrase that can be interpreted as a requirement, or from which a requirement can reasonably be inferred. Also highlight any phrase that indicates a benefit for the user associated with a highlighted requirement.
2. **Articulate requirements:** for each highlighted phrase, create a free-standing description of the requirement, or inferred requirement. Where available, create a free standing description of the associated benefit.
3. **Review requirements:** ask the user representative to review the extracted requirements, to confirm that they do properly reflect the scenario described, or to clarify any misunderstandings there may be in our interpretation of the scenario. This review process may also elicit additional requirements and/or benefits that can be included

2.2 GWAS scenario

In this scenario researcher Kristina will take the result of a genome wide association study experiment and a metabolomics experiment (SNPs related to metabolites) and map it to biological concepts using text mining technology. The general research cycle is summarized in Figure 1. First Kristina and colleagues define the research problem based on previous work (Fig. 1, step 1). The GWAS and metabolomics experiments were done by others than Kristina, so she makes a note of the origin (including the still confidential research proposal for the study). The initial hypothesis is that the Metabolomic Syndrome (MetS) traits are complex traits characterized by specific metabolite signatures. The genetics of these metabolite signatures explain an important part of the missing heritability of MetS traits. It is yet unknown which biological processes that are affected by these signatures.

At step 2 Kristina selects the data and workflows to work with. Kristina is new to workflows, so she wishes to start with an existing workflow. When she started on the project she was introduced to people that perform related work. She knows that one of her colleagues is making a workflow for the mapping of SNPs to genes, and then onto pathways. She also knows that another colleague has created an abstract workflow for parts

of the text mining technology that she wants to use. She wishes to understand these workflows and asks her colleagues to explain their functionality to her. She decides that she would like to build a workflow that would integrate the text mining technology with the one already implemented for the SNP-gene-pathway pipeline. However, the abstract workflow for the text mining technology will probably take a long time to implement since the underlying web services that are needed are not all at 'production level' yet. She is dependent on another colleague to implement these for her. At step 3, Kristina makes her own abstract workflow that she will use as a reference when explaining her research and analysis steps. Until the web services that she needs are available, she will use another tool to do the actual analysis. This tool is however in need of an update, which she will perform. In the meantime, the ordering customer, which is the scientist that provided the original data, is getting impatient and wants results. Therefore, she decides to perform the execution step 4 by running the analysis with the version of the monolithic tool that is available¹. Eventually, the executable version of the abstract workflow will replicate this analysis and allow greater flexibility in experiment design. She uses the output from the already available SNP-gene-pathway workflow to map SNPs to genes, ending up with a list of genes for a metabolite. This list she feeds into the tool.

At this stage the results may suggest for example that one gene in the set of genes associated with a specific metabolite actually is associated with the metabolite via the Gluconeogenesis biological process. It is one of the two main mechanisms humans and many other animals use to keep blood glucose levels from dropping too low (hypoglycaemia), information he finds on the Internet. She makes a note of that and goes back to the tool to see if Gluconeogenesis is a process that is known to be associated with MetS. She will perform the same type of analysis for the different genes associated with the metabolite, and also for the list of genes as a whole. These analyses will lead to a number of candidate biological processes hypothesized to explain the gene-metabolite associations. This is now her interpretation of her experiment that she wishes to link to her experiment and the processed data. Kristina notes that in a next cycle she will want to perform another workflow that compares her results using text mining with the results from the already available SNP-gene-pathway workflow. In this case she will link the result from this workflow to the previous experiment and in particular to the initial hypothesis. At some point, she wishes to be able to retrieve this past information and the interrelationships among his hypotheses.

When her findings and new hypotheses are valuable and novel, she will publish her results (step 5). The publication has cleaned information, sufficient for evaluating her hypothesis and rerunning the one workflow and the one dataset that lead to this result.

¹ <http://biosemantics.org/anni>

Figure 1: General Research Cycle

2.3 Extracted requirements

The following table contains a list of the main requirements stemming from the analysis of the GWAS scenario in terms of the different identified user roles (creators, reusers, and publishers) and their specific needs. The table also reflects the effects of addressing such requirements both in terms of the particular goals that need to be addressed and the specific benefits and impact derived from doing so.

As a...	I want...	So that...	Benefit	Impact
			(for me)	(to all)
Creator	to record the origin of experimental data used for analysis	I can acknowledge data providers	2	5
Creator	to record information that must be kept confidential	I can access information directly in order to save time while still maintaining confidentiality	4	2
Re-user	to adapt existing workflows for a new study	I can benefit from the knowledge and previous work of colleagues	5	4
Re-user	to understand existing workflows	I can benefit from the knowledge and previous work of colleagues	5	4
Creator	to build a new workflow from more than one existing workflow	I can benefit from the knowledge and previous work of colleagues	5	4

Creator	to record an abstract (not-yet-implemented) workflow	I can explain my needs to colleagues who will implement processes I shall need	3	2
Creator	to partially execute a workflow, with unavailable sections replaced by manual processes	I can make progress in my research while waiting for processing tools or other workflows to be implemented	5	3
Contributor	to record edited workflow components	I can inform my collaborator of the processing tool (web services) development progress	3	3
Creator	to record information that is discovered from other external sources	I can keep track of reasons for decisions made in the conduct of my studies	4	4
Creator	to repeatedly re-run a workflow with different input parameters and/or data	I can look for potential links between my results and other known biological mechanisms	5	5
Publisher	to record an interpretation of results obtained, linked to the experimental record and input data used	I can organize my information for me, my colleagues and later publication	5	5
Publisher	to record notes for future work	I can organize my information for me, my colleagues and later publication	5	5
Publisher	link workflow results to previous results, procedures and hypotheses	I can subsequently retrieve information about the relationship between hypotheses and results obtained	5	5
Publisher	Extract information from a working RO for publication	I can easily use my working notes as a basis for creating the distilled information needed for publication.	5	5

3. Relation of GWAS requirements to Wf4Ever technical components

3.1 WP2 RO modelling and workflow management

The requirements gathered by Kristina's analysis pinpoint many technical requirements that need to be considered by the modeling and management of research objects. A research object can be thought of as a bundle of resources that are used, produced or referenced within a scientific investigation. Examples of resources that can be aggregated within a research object include the workflow, which implements the scientific experiment, provenances traces that are obtained by executing the workflow and annotations that describe the workflow and associated provenance traces.

The main technical requirements that can be derived from the user requirements presented in this document are as follows:

- **Workflows should be annotated to allow scientists understand the experiments they implement:** as mentioned in Kristina's analysis, she had some difficulties in understanding what the existing workflow that she wishes to reuse does. If annotation that describes such a workflow existed, Kristina would have spent less time trying to understand the analysis the workflow implements.
- Abstract workflows as a means for understanding existing experiments and designing new ones. A key notion that was mentioned in Kristina's analysis is that of abstract workflow. Such a workflow provides a high lever description of the experiment, its constituents steps, without specifying the services (or components) that are used to perform the steps. Abstract workflows can be used to understand existing experiments, and can also be used to design new experiments in the absence of services able to implement the steps required.
- Discovering workflows and services. The tool responsible for managing research objects should provide a means for retrieving the services and workflows that are of interest to the user.
- Composing existing workflows. From the requirements gathered by Kristina, it transpired that she wanted to create a new workflow by composing existing ones. Therefore, the workbench provided to specify workflows should provide this feature.

3.2 WP3 Collaboration and recommendation

Regarding WP3 Workflow Evolution, Sharing and Collaboration the relation between the GWAS requirements and the WP3 technical components we establish the following relationships:

- As a **creator** Kristina may wish to build a new workflow from more than one existing workflow so that she can benefit from the knowledge and previous work of colleagues. This GWAS requirement is intimately connected with the recommender system, that should provide:

- **Reputation based recommendations.** Kristina as the creator of a new workflow must be aware of the relevant workflows which content might be of her interest. As it can be extracted from the GWAS scenario, the strength to the recommendation assigned by the recommender system to each workflow (or RO as a whole) must take into account the opinion of Kristina's colleagues working on the respective research fields.
- **Content-based recommendations.** Kristina when creating or searching new workflows knows certain keywords that might appear in relevant workflows (or ROs) (e.g. "Metabolomic Syndrome", "MetS", etc.). The recommender system should provide content-based recommendations based on the way search and retrieving of scientific content is already performed by researchers; allowing thus the search of such keywords in workflows (or ROs).
- **Cold-start problem aware recommendations.** Kristina as a creator might interact for the first time with the recommender system. The recommender system should provide her recommendations, even though there might not be sufficient ratings information or profile information to sketch her preferences using conventional recommendation techniques.
- As a **re-user** Kristina might want to adapt existing workflows for a new study so that she can benefit from the knowledge and previous work of colleagues. This requirement is related in the same manner with the recommender system; but is also related RO collaboration and evolution model. More precisely this model should provide:
 - **Comparison capability.** Kristina as a re-user will need to compare different versions of a RO, or the RO she is building with ROs. Kristina should also have a perfect understanding of how the RO has changed from a previous state to analyze the transformations, or to find her individual contributions to the RO.
 - **Versioning capability.** Kristina as a re-user might need to keep different versions of a workflow (or a RO). Versions should consider changes at different levels, from the RO itself, its metadata, or the resources it encapsulates.
 - **Roll-Back capability.** Kristina when re-using a RO may want to go back to a previous state of the ROs to discard new changes that she has introduced.
 - **Fix and diagnose capability.** The RO collaboration and evolution model should in some situations offer to Kristina a diagnosis of the errors introduced; and if possible, guidance about how to fix them. To this end, a complete log of the changes performed and how they were performed will be required.
- Finally, the rest of GWAS requirements that imply the modification of ROs are also related with the RO Collaboration and Evolution model in the same fashion that we have already described.

3.3 WP4 Integrity and Authenticity

Integration with the Integrity and Authenticity (I&A) services: By the use of provenance and I&A services Kristina would be able to evaluate the quality and the health of the resources that she wants to re-use. For instance, she could trace how the GWAS input data was produced and where it came from, or she could increase her trust in the method by reproducing how the results were produced, or how many times it was reused and evaluated positively. Therefore each one of the components has been previously analyzed by the I&A service. Furthermore, the RO that she has created and all the work she is doing on it will generate provenance and would help other users to discover her work. It will be interesting to herself to evaluate her own RO so she can find out lacks in her research. It will be useful even after the publication of the research because it will provide interesting information for retrieving and earning recognition.

The main links to the I&A service can be summarized in:

- Use of previously analyzed I&A provenance quality of workflows to obtain feedback during the composition of a new workflow (related to the requirements: (1) to build a new workflow from more than one existing workflow; (2) to adapt existing workflows for a new study).
- Use of previously analyzed I&A Minimal Information Model quality of ROs to obtain a feedback about the confidence over the elements contained on it. It could be used to trust or not in the results obtained or to get a quick overview of the RO by other users (related to the requirement: extract information from a working RO publication).
- Use of provenance execution traces to track the quality of the experiment and to allow its inspection and reutilization by other users (related to the requirement: to understand existing workflows).

4. Conclusions

In this addendum we extended D6.1 with results from analysing the requirements for preservation of workflows that help interpret the results of GWA studies. We added a detailed and 'real-life' scenario for GWAS, taking a complete research cycle into account. This scenario provided new user requirements for the Wf4Ever technical workpackages that were used for new technical requirements and implemented in the Wf4Ever architecture. The main preservation requirements coming out of the GWAS requirements analysis relate to annotations to a large extent. This is not unique to GWA studies, but was also stressed in the WP6 Genomics Wf4Ever delivered technical report [1], and by the WP5 Astronomy in a Wf4Ever wiki document². Annotations on individual components of the RO (for example workflow, inputs, and outputs) will help to understand the contents of an RO and thereby reproduce a preserved scientific method. For example, for an individual workflow, information for authoring, description and dataset examples could be provided. Eventually, the annotation needs have to be matched by the RO model ontology and associated domain ontologies, as well as in the auto-generated information provided by future Wf4Ever tools or services. Annotating RO content with simple tools (e.g. text documents) during development will help elucidate missing classes or relations in the ontologies and wf4ever tooling.

² <http://www.wf4ever-project.org/wiki/display/docs/Users+requirements+on+annotations>

5. References

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